

CHARACTERS OF MBA STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Jupiter is the planet for money and Mercury is the planet for knowledge. Both the above planets make one an expert. The particular field is chosen by other planets which has conjunction with Jupiter and Mercury. Money is essential for our survival. Knowledge is also essential for our survival. Without money we can't live. Without knowledge we can't live.

Key Words: Astrology – Science – Saints – Eternal – Guidance – Planes & Bhava for MBA – Planets Effects in MBA Branches – Common Characters – of Fire Signs – Earth Signs – Airy Signs – Water Signs – Planets for Leader Ship – Karagas of Jupiter and Mercury – Karagas of 4/5/9 and 10th bhava.

Introduction:

Master of Business Administration is the most valuable course for students. Because the MBA students earn lot of money. There are so, many branches in MBA. We can easily understand the characters of MBA students by their birth sign.

History of MBA:

Commerce was started in Portugal in 1759, later developed as Master of Business Administration . In India in 1886 Commerce course was started in Pachaiyappa College Chennai, Said by researchers. In 1903 the British government introduced commerce courses in Presidency college, Kolkata. MBA was introduced in india in 1968 at University of Delhi.

Planets for MBA:

Jupiter is the planet for finance (money) and administration. Mercury is the planet for commerce and marketing. So, both are the planets for MBA study.

Jupiter:

Jupiter has wisdom and highly intuition power, expert in politics, finance, genius, minister, leader and business man.

Mercury:

Mercury has humor sense, expert in maths, astrology, knowledge, messaging, communication and marketing.

Bhavas for MBA:

4/5/9 and 10th bhavas help to study MBA successfully.

- 4th Bhava: It is the bhava for education and brain power. It also helps to improve our thoughts and knowledge.
- 5th Bhava: It is the bhava for intelligence, sixth sense, wisdom, meditation; subconscious mind and face the situation easily.
- 9th Bhava: It is the bhava for higher education, post graduate education, respect to elders and prestige.
- 10th Bhava: It is the bhava for power, status, business, travels, agriculture, government jobs, higher posts and good karma.

Planetary Affects on MBA Branches:

1. MBA (Finance):

One who wants to shine in MBA (Finance) Mercury and Jupiter should be powerful in their horoscope. They would stand in their own house or they would stand in their exaltation house.

2. M.B.A. Marketing Mercury and Venus:

One who wants to shine in MBA (Marketing) Mercury and Venus should be powerful in their horoscope. They would stand in their own house or they would stand in their exaltation house.

3. M.B.A. Management Science:

One who wants to shine in MBA (Management Science) Moon, Jupiter, Saturn and Venus should be powerful in their horoscope. They would stand in their own house or they would stand in their exaltation house.

4. M.B.A. Management Information System:

One who wants to shine in MBA (Management information system) Mercury, Rahu, Ketu and Venus should be powerful in their horoscope. They would stand in their own house or they would stand in their exaltation house.

5. M.B.A. Mathematics for Management:

One who wants to shine in MBA (Mathematics for Management) Mercury, and Mars should be powerful in their horoscope. They would stand in their own house or they would stand in their exaltation house.

6. M.B.A. General Management:

One who wants to shine in MBA (General Management) Jupiter, and Venus should be powerful in their horoscope. They would stand in their own house or they would stand in their exaltation house.

7. M.B.A. Data Analytics:

One who wants to shine in MBA (Data Analytics) Sun and Mars should be powerful in their horoscope. They would stand in their own house or they would stand in their exaltation house.

8. M.B.A. Operations Management:

One who wants to shine in MBA (Operations Management) Jupiter, Mercury and Mars should be powerful in their horoscope. They would stand in their own house or they would stand in their exaltation house.

9. M.B.A. Risk Management:

One who wants to shine in MBA (Risk Management) Jupiter, Mercury and Sun should be powerful in their horoscope. They would stand in their own house or they would stand in their exaltation house.

10. M.B.A. Administration Management:

One who wants to shine in MBA (Administration Management) Jupiter, Mercury and Sun should be powerful in their horoscope. They would stand in their own house or they would stand in their exaltation house.

11. M.B.A. Project Management:

One who wants to shine in MBA (Project Management) Jupiter, Mars, Saturn, Rahu and Sun should be powerful in their horoscope. They would stand in their own house or they would stand in their exaltation house.

Division of Signs:

1. According to Kendra 1/4/7/10:

Movable signs	-	Aries, Cancer, Libra, Capricorn
Immovable signs	-	Taurus, Leo, Scorpio, Aquarius
Dual signs	-	Gemini, Virgo, Sagittarius, Pisces

2. According to trine 1/5/9:

Fire signs	-	Aries, Leo, Sagittarius
Earth signs	-	Taurus, Virgo, Capricorn
Air signs	-	Gemini, Libra, Aquarius
Water signs	-	Cancer, Scorpio, Pisces

General Characters of MBA Students born in Fire Signs:

They should always have obedience and discipline. They never have selfish mind. They will reach higher level in researches and top positions in their profession.

General Characters of MBA Students born in Earth Signs:

They are very honest persons. They are always sincere in their duties. Higher status and respect should be given to them. They will shine in both government and private sectors.

General Characters of MBA Students born in Air Signs:

They are always have done their works with speed like the air. They never like others advice. They have imaginative power. They will win by their best argument. They are always vigilant. They are always dedicated.

General Characters of MBA Students born in Water Signs:

They work always without rest. They are always active they have positive attitude. They have reached the higher position in earlier age. They frequently shift their companies.

General Characters of MBA Students born in Movable Signs:

They are always bold and courage. They work hard until reach the success. Sometimes they will do negative activities (short cut) for success.

General Characters of MBA Students born immovable fire signs:

They have never inferiority complex in their life. They always take decision very fast. They are always independent. They are always praised by others.

General Characters of MBA Students born immovable earth signs:

They always attract their enemies by their love. They should sacrifice everything for their belongings. They will develop step by step. They are always light hearted persons. They should run their companies very best.

General Characters of MBA Students born in movable air signs:

They should make their companies profitable one. Dedication is their special quality. They always have humanity. Positive thoughts are their plus point. They frequently shift their companies.

General Characters of MBA Students born in movable water signs:

They are always active. They attract others by their sweet speech. They are always with self-control. In administration they have creative power. They not only improve themselves but also improve their co-worker

General Characters of MBA Students born in immovable signs:

They should tackle the problems cleverly. Their activities are stable, never vanished. They should think clearly. Their knowledge is power.

General Characters of MBA Students born in immovable fire signs:

Expert in business. They should attain higher post easily. Never obey to others. Kindness to labours. Solve all problems easily.

General Characters of MBA Students born in immovable earth signs:

They have higher thoughts and good habits. They motivate others by their sweetest speech. They are the bridge to the company owners and labours.

General Characters of MBA Students born in immovable air signs:

They always respect others. They are always vigilant. They have high memory power. They have leadership quality. They explain the duties to labours very well.

General Characters of MBA Students born in immovable water signs:

They are hard workers. They always motivate their labours. Never fear about anything. They never affect by feelings. They are always vigilant and improve their status step by step.

General Characters of MBA Students born in dual signs:

They always change their mind and attitudes. They have dual qualities. They are always instable. Their feelings are always change.

General Characters of MBA Students born in dual fire signs:

They always keep justice and obey justice. They always show sympathy to others. They should reach their goal very easily. They should reach their higher level without any effort.

General Characters of MBA Students born in dual earth signs:

They always work hard. They never obey others. They are always vigilant. They should never change their attitude. They do anything only for their profit.

General Characters of MBA Students born in dual air signs:

They should always act fast. They are very clever. They should say advice to others. They explain wisdom to others. They always work hard. They should give double profit to their companies.

General Characters of MBA Students born in dual water Signs:

They never show their higher thoughts to others. They always help others. Forgive and forget is their noble quality. They are successful in foreign business.

Leadership Qualities Related Planets:

- Sukla paksha Moon is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and positive attitude.
- Venus is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and full faith in skill.
- Mars is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and doing challenging tasks.
- Mercury is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and responsible behaviour.
- Sun is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and time management.
- Jupiter is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and Welfare of labours.
- Rahu is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and creativity.
- Kethu is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and service mind.
- Mars is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and perfect activities.
- Jupiter is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and maintain human relationship.
- Sun is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and production development.
- Mars is the karaga planet for the leadership quality, bravery and self-control.
- Sun is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and decision making.
- Jupiter is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and pucca plan.
- Saturn is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and hard work.
- Jupiter is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and carrying full responsibility.
- Mars is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and efforts till reach the goal.
- Venus & Mercury is the karaga planet for the leadership quality and innovative thinking.

Conclusion:

Positive attitude, full faith in skill, doing challenging tasks, responsible behaviour, time management, Welfare of labours, creativity, service mind, perfect activities, maintain human relationship, production development, bravery and self-control, decision making, pucca plan, hard work, carrying full responsibility, efforts till reach the goal, innovative thinking are the best qualities for MBA students.

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